

Question of State in Quantum Single Particle Bound State Entropy

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In (1) it is argued that von Neumann's density operator $d = \sum_i b_i |i\rangle\langle i| = \sum_j m_j |j\rangle\langle j|$ where in one case $|i\rangle$ represents an orthonormal basis and in the other of $|j\rangle$ a different nonorthogonal basis is used. The problem is that von Neumann entropy $-\sum_i b_i \ln(b_i)$ and $-\sum_j m_j \ln(m_j)$ are not the same, they depend on the projection operator used. The author of (1) goes on to argue that historically it was suggested this might mean that a quantum state in quantum statistical mechanics is not defined clearly.

We wish to consider the case of a pure bound state for which we have defined $S = \text{entropy} = S_p + S_x$ where $S_p = -\int dp P(p) \ln(P(p))$ and $S_x = -\int dx P(x) \ln(P(x))$. According to quantum mechanics, one may not know p and x exactly, but $S = S_p + S_x$ is equivalent to using $P(p)P(x)$ in Shannon's entropy formula. (Alternatively, one may use $P(p/x)P(x)$.) As a result, the so-called state (x,p) associated with $P(p)P(x)$ assumes knowledge of p and x exactly and so is not a real quantum state perhaps in the manner suggested in (1).

In order to consider this issue, we argue that a quantum bound problem may be thought of in two ways: the classical mechanics type picture, and the statistical mechanical type one. The first approach is consistent with using the wavefunction $W(x)$ in the time-independent Schrodinger equation. $P(p)$ and $P(x)$ do not appear, but this is still a statistical picture because $KE(x) = \{\sum_p p^2/2m a(p) \exp(ipx)\}/W(x)$. $KE(x) + V(x) = E$, nevertheless, has the form of a classical mechanical particle. In other words, it has one total E at any x and a potential value $V(x)$ at x . In fact, $KE(x)$ may be considered to represent a $v_{rms}(x)$ which is the velocity of the classical particle, although this is a purely mathematical construct. One may define $P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx)/W(x)$ which is complex and allows for interference among $\exp(ipx)$ so this picture is very different from that of usual classical probabilities.

The second picture of quantum mechanics involves $P(x)$ or $P(p)$ which behave as classical probabilities (i.e. are real, positive and sum to 1). For example: Operator ave = $\langle W | B | W \rangle$ is associated with this picture (as is von Neumann's density matrix). One may write energy as: $E = \sum_p P(p) p^2/2m + \sum_x V(x) P(x)$, but this equation does not lead to solutions. One must use the Schrodinger equation to solve for $W(x)$ and find $a(p)$ from $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ and then form $P(x) = W(x)W(x)$ and $P(p) = a(p)a(p)$. Nevertheless quantum statistics, in order to be linked with classical statistical mechanics, seems to be formulated in terms of $P(p)$ and $P(x)$. For example the diagonal elements of von Neumann's density matrix contain this type of probability.

Given that quantum mechanics may be viewed in two different statistical manners, (A) in terms of $W(x)$, the Schrodinger equation and $P(p/x)$ or (B) in terms of $P(p)$ and $P(x)$, a formulation of quantum statistical mechanics based on $P(p)$ and $P(x)$ may lead to unusual results. In particular, $P(p)$ and $P(x)$ represent exact p and x values, but according to quantum theory one cannot know these at the same time. Thus talking of $P(p)$ and $P(x)$ (in a classical way) seems to mean referring to a quantum state that is not really defined, perhaps one of the states noted in (1). This may not be a problem, however, if the underlying statistics follows from $W(x)$ and $a(p)$ and $P(p/x)$ for which p and x are defined, but are linked to complex probabilities.

Issues with von Neumann's Density Operator?

Schrodinger and later J.L. Park and many others have noted that von Neumann's density operator $\rho = \sum_i b_i |i\rangle\langle i| = \sum_j m_j |j\rangle\langle j|$ leads to ambiguity as described in (1). For instance the entropy $S = -\sum_i b_i \ln(b_i)$ does not equal $S = -\sum_j m_j \ln(m_j)$ and so a resolution is needed. In (1) it is stated that J.L. Park considered that a quantum state may not be well-defined as a consequence.

We consider the case of the entropy of a bound single particle state which we define as $S = S_p + S_x$. This follows from Shannon's entropy $-\sum_i P(i) \ln(P(i))$ with $P(i) = P(x)P(p)$ if one integrates over p and x . Such a product probability, however, assumes knowing p and x exactly which opposes quantum theory. Thus it seems that such a result makes use of a fictitious state of (x,p) which mimics a classical phase space state.

In order to resolve this issue, we consider the quantum description of a single bound particle in two ways.

Classical Mechanical Approach to a Single Bound Quantum Particle

We argue that the usual time-independent Schrodinger equation mimics in a sense the classical mechanical equation of a particle i.e.

$$KE(x) + V(x) = E \quad ((1))$$

Here one has 1 particle which has a potential of $V(x)$ at x and an energy E everywhere. The only unusual aspect is

$$KE(x) = \{-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} W(x) \frac{d}{dx} W(x)\} / W(x) = \{\sum_p a(p) \frac{p^2}{2m} \exp(ipx)\} / W(x) \quad ((2))$$

Thus statistical aspects already exist in this so-called classical mechanical picture. One needs to use $v_{rms}(x)$ from $KE(x)$ to identify a classical velocity and this is simply a math construct. Nevertheless, ((1)) is in the form of an equation for a single classical mechanical particle. ((2)) makes use of $W(x)$, but nowhere do $P(x)$ and $P(p)$ appear.

Given that statistics are already present in ((2)) one may define:

$$P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx) / W(x). \quad ((3))$$

This is complex, involves interference from $\exp(ipx)$, but a sum of p yields 1. Thus in this picture p and x are well defined at each x point, but one deals with complex probabilities. We have shown in (2) that one may define $P(p) = W(x)W(x)$ and $P(x) = a(p)a(p)$ from ((3)), but this leads to a completely different picture, namely a classical statistical mechanical one.

Classical Statistical Mechanical Picture of Single Quantum Bound Particle

In the above picture one uses $V(x)$ to describe the potential energy of a single particle. If one writes $V(x)P(x)$, however, this suggests a statistical system with many particles as one has a density $= P(x)$. (In fact there is only one particle, but it has different probabilities to be at different x points.) Using $P(x)$, however, is a classical statistical mechanical approach. In particular, $\langle W \rangle$ (used in the von Neumann approach) makes use of the density or classical statistical mechanical view of quantum mechanics. In particular, one may consider:

$$E = \sum \text{over } p \quad p^2/2m P(p) + \sum \text{over } x \quad V(x) P(x) \quad ((4))$$

((4)) mixes $P(p)$ and $P(x)$ and is classical in the sense that $P(p)P(x)$ seems to represent a classical phase point (p,x) . Quantum mechanics, however, does not allow for p and x to be known exactly at the same time so we argue that this is a fictitious state as discussed in (1). Given that $P(p)$ and $P(x)$ appear in ((4)), one may try to create a Shannon's entropy based on $P(p,x) = P(p)P(x)$ yielding $S = S_p + S_x$.

It may be noted that ((4)) contains $P(p)$ and $P(x)$, but does not yield solutions for these. One must solve the Schrodinger equation and find $W(x)$ and then $a(p)$. There have been attempts in the literature (3) to write the Schrodinger equation in terms of density and make it appear as a hydrodynamical equation. In such a case, one would argue that there are not two pictures, the classical mechanical single particle view and the classical statistical mechanical view using density. In (3), however, it is argued that if a velocity field is 0 (as in the bound case) there exists a potential such that:

$$-d/dx B(x) - d/dx V(x) = 0 \rightarrow B(x) + V(x) = E \quad ((5))$$

This is the conservation equation for a single classical mechanical particle with $B(x) = KE(x)$. Thus, writing $W(x) = \sqrt{\text{density}}$ in the Schrodinger equation (which holds in some cases) does not change it into an equation describing classical statistical mechanics or hydrodynamics. It is still an equation of a single particle in terms of classical mechanics as ((5)) shows with the exception that $KE(x)$ is statistical.

As a result, we argue that a quantum mechanical single bound particle must be thought of in terms of two pictures, one which describes a classical mechanical particle (but with a statistical kinetic energy at each x) and the other a statistical mechanical picture using density.

Formulating quantum statistical mechanics in terms of the latter may lead to some unusual results, for example a curious fictitious state (x,p) linked to $P(p)P(x)$ with p and x being exactly known because in the classical mechanical single particle picture they are exactly known. Thus $P(p)P(x)$ uses classical probabilities (positive, less than 1 which sum to 1), but the state with p and x known exactly is fictitious. This may be one of the fictitious quantum states discussed in (1).

Conclusion

In conclusion, classical statistical mechanics is based on $P(x)$ and $P(p)$. Quantum mechanics also contains these probabilities, but they are created from a more fundamental picture namely one which uses the wavefunction $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ and the time-independent Schrodinger equation which has the form of classical mechanical equation for a single particle, albeit with a statistical kinetic energy at x namely $\{-1/2m d/dx dW/dx\} / W = \{\sum_p a(p) p^2/2m \exp(ipx)\} / W$. In such a picture x and p are known exactly at each x , but one has complex probabilities which involve interference i.e $P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx) / W(x)$. One may create $P(p)$ and $P(x)$ for a single bound particle from these i.e. $a(p)a(p)$ and $W(x)W(x)$ and so have the appearance of classical statistical mechanics, but we argue this is just an appearance. One may also argue that one may replace $W(x)$ in the time-independent Schrodinger equation with $\sqrt{\text{density}}$ and so eliminate, so to speak, the single particle picture, but that is not the case, because even though $KE(x)$ is written in terms of density the essential equation is $B(x)+V(x)=E$ where $B(x) = KE(x)$ which is the classical mechanical equation for a single particle, not a hydrodynamical equation.

Given that one may create $P(p)$ and $P(x)$, one may consider a single bound particle Shannon's entropy based on $P = P(p)P(x)$ leading to $S = S_p + S_x$. $P(p)P(x)$ suggests a fictitious quantum state (p,x) (because p and x cannot simultaneously be known exactly) which mimics the classical (p,x) . We argue that this may be a fictitious quantum state of the nature suggested in (1).

References

1. Beretta, GP The Hatsopoulos-Gyftopoulos resolution of the Schrodinger-Park paradox about the concept of "state" in quantum statistical mechanics. (2006)
Researchgate /quant-ph0610057.pdf
2. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Does Quantum Thermodynamics Dictate the Form of the Wavefunction $P(x)=W^*(x)W(x)$? (preprint, zenodo, 2022)
3. Kaniadakis, G. Statistical Origins of Quantum Mechanics (2018)
<https://arxiv.org/pdf/quant-ph/0112049.pdf>